

ON THE ISOTHERMAL STUDY OF THE CONDENSED TERNARY SYSTEM
DICYANOBISETHYLENEDIAMINE-COBALTIC SULPHATE, COPPER
SULPHATE AND WATER

BY BYOMKES SARMA

The condensed ternary system-dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate, copper sulphate and water has been studied at 30°. Formation of the double salt dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cuprisulphate, $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been definitely established as a result. The double salt is rather unstable in water, but is stable in copper sulphate solution.

The double salt, dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cuprisulphate has been described in a previous communication (Rây and Sarma, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 59). Its composition is given by $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In order to verify this composition and with a view to making a detailed examination of the subject, the ternary system-dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate, copper sulphate and water has been studied at 30°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Reagents.—Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate (cf. Rây and Sarma, *loc. cit.*) was thrice recrystallised from hot water.

Pure copper sulphate was recrystallised thrice from hot water and dried at the room temperature. (Found: Cu, 25.47; S, 12.79; H_2O , 36.01. Calc. for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 25.48; S, 12.8; H_2O , 36.05 per cent).

Methods of Analysis.—The solution (5 c.c.) was taken out of the reaction vessel with a pipette fitted with a glass wool plug. This was weighed and diluted to 100 c.c. Aliquot parts were taken for individual analysis. Copper was determined iodimetrically. The amount of complex sulphate was determined indirectly. For this the total sulphate was determined gravimetrically and then making allowance for copper present, the amount of the complex sulphate was calculated; 1 g. $\text{SO}_4^{2-} \sim 5.812$ g. of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate.

Equilibrium Determinations

The procedure adopted was to make up a saturated solution at some 20° above the temperature at which the reaction was studied. In this case, a saturated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate was made at 50°; 100 c.c. of this solution were taken in a cylindrical glass reaction vessel of about 200 c.c. capacity, provided with a cork, through the centre of which passed the rod of the glass stirrer, operated mechanically. At the margin of the stopper, there was a hole for pipetting off the liquid phase to determine its composition. The hole was kept closed with a glass stopper as long as the reaction was carried on. The reaction vessel, with its contents, was placed in a thermostat regulated at $30.0 \pm 0.02^\circ$ and stirring carried

on mechanically for days together until equilibrium was attained, as indicated by no further change in the composition of the liquid. During this time a solid phase separated out. After the solid phase had been allowed to settle, about 5 c.c. of the liquid phase were taken out with a pipette fitted with a special glass wool filtering arrangement at the tip, weighed and diluted to 100 c.c. Suitable portions of this were used for analysis. When equilibrium was established, the solid phase was rapidly separated from the liquid by filtration on a Buchner funnel. The liquid was drained as much as possible and then a suitable portion (0.5 g.) of the solid was taken in a weighing bottle, weighed and dissolved in water to a measured volume. Suitable portions of the latter were analysed to determine the composition of the solid phase. The liquid adhering to the separated solid phase is typical of the liquid phase with which the solid is in equilibrium. Delay in filtration and in weighing the solid phase was avoided as much as possible so that no appreciable loss due to evaporation of water took place. From the first set of the experiment, the solubility of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate in water at 30° was obtained. Then mixtures of about 100 c.c. of the saturated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate at 50° and increasing amounts of copper sulphate were taken in the reaction vessel, and the contents were dissolved by warming on the water-bath. The vessel was then placed in the thermostat and operated as before.

For a few sets of mixtures, the composition of the dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate increased in the liquid phase and mainly this separated as the solid phase. Then the amount of the complex sulphate began to decrease till it became almost constant in the liquid phase and both dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and copper sulphate as the double salt separated out of the solution. This happened for about 10 sets of mixture when no further increase of copper sulphate in solution took place.

On the other side of the system, there was pure copper sulphate to start with and its solubility at 30° was determined as in the case of the other constituent. Then mixtures of about 100 c.c. of a supersaturated solution of copper sulphate and increasing amounts of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate were taken in the reaction vessel and operated as before. Amount of copper sulphate increased gradually with the increase of the complex sulphate and accidentally the eutectic mixture was obtained when two phases, the yellowish green double salt and the blue copper sulphate, separated simultaneously from the liquid phase. The results are plotted on a triangular graph and the junctions of the curves give the eutectic points. The mixture of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and copper sulphate corresponding to the first eutectic derived from the curve was taken in the reaction vessel with water and operated as usual to ascertain its composition more definitely.

The results of analysis of the various saturated solutions and the corresponding solid phases separated are given in Table I for triangular and in Table II for the rectangular graph.

The experimental results given in Table I are best represented by Roozeboom's triangular graph, in Fig. 1. The vertices W, A and B of the equilateral triangle WAB represent 100% of water, dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and copper sulphate

TABLE I

Liquid phase (% composition)			Solid phase (% composition)			Nature of solid phase.
X ₂ SO ₄ .	CuSO ₄ .	H ₂ O.	X ₂ SO ₄ .	CuSO ₄ .	H ₂ O.	
2.51	0.0	97.49	91.16	0.0	8.84	X ₂ SO ₄ · 3H ₂ O
2.86	1.09	96.05	91.16	0.0	8.84	
3.07	1.89	95.04	70.06	0.50	29.44	"
3.62	2.50	93.88	72.02	0.80	27.18	"
3.90	2.76	93.34	51.87	16.38	31.75	Hydrated double salt + X ₂ SO ₄ · 3H ₂ O. Eutectic 1.
3.66	2.74	93.60	37.66	21.72	40.62	
3.28	2.86	93.86	39.07	23.80	37.13	Double salt hydrate
2.75	3.24	94.01	20.06	14.94	65.00	
2.48	3.81	93.71	50.17	28.58	21.25	
2.36	5.89	91.75	—	—	—*	
2.38	7.52	90.10	—	—	—*	
2.45	9.76	87.79	51.89	30.10	18.01	
2.51	11.63	85.86	45.94	27.38	26.68	
2.51	14.01	83.48	33.02	24.08	42.90	
0.0	19.66	80.34	0.0	63.95	36.05	
0.57	19.94	79.49	0.0	64.07	35.93	
1.08	20.22	78.70	0.50	62.95	36.55	
1.47	20.44	78.09	0.41	63.28	36.31	
1.96	20.25	77.79	0.60	62.76	36.64	
2.08	20.59	77.33	0.0	64.28 ⁿ	35.72	
2.33	20.85	76.82	0.73	63.04	36.23	
2.48	20.89	76.63	35.81	42.14	22.05	

* In this case the solid phase was too small for analysis.

FIG. 1

respectively. The sides of the triangle represent the binary system and any point within the triangle represents the ternary system and the perpendicular distance of the point from the different arms gives the composition of the constituent represented at the opposite vertex. It will be observed that the straight lines joining the points, indicating the composition of the liquid phase and the corresponding separated solid phase, all pass through the point which indicates the composition of the solid phase with which the various liquid phases are in equilibrium.

The diagram (Fig. 1) consists of three separate saturation curves, 'ac', 'cd' and 'db' and various complex areas.

From the figure it is evident that 54.64 g. of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and 31.25 g. of copper sulphate are the percentage proportions present in the hydrated double salt. It is also evident that the double salt is not very stable with respect to water at 30° and that the stability of the double salt increases with the increasing amounts of copper sulphate in solution.

TABLE II

Liquid phases Composition of 100 g. of the solute			Solid phases in equilibrium Composition of 100 g. of the anhydrous salts			Nature of the solid phases	
[Co(CN) ₂ (en) ₂]SO ₄ [A]	CuSO ₄ [B]	Water in which 100 g. of the solute dissolved to form a satd. soln.	[Co(CN) ₂ (en) ₂]SO ₄ [A]	CuSO ₄ [B]	Water per 100 g. of the anhydrous salts.		
100.0	0.0	3985.0 g.	100.0	0.0	9.70 g.	A	
72.41	27.59	2432.0	100.0	0.0	9.70		
61.89	38.11	1916.0	99.28	0.72	41.72		
59.14	40.86	1534.0	98.91	1.09	37.34		
58.56	41.44	1402.0	76.00	24.00	46.52	A + double salt. Eutectic No.1.	
57.19	42.81	1462.0	63.42	36.58	68.39	Double salt	
53.42	46.58	1529.0	62.15	37.85	59.05		
45.91	54.09	1570.0	57.31	42.69	185.70		
39.43	60.57	1489.0	63.69	36.31	26.98		
28.61	71.39	1112.0	—	—	—		
24.04	75.96	910.0	—	—	—		
20.06	79.94	719.0	63.28	36.72	21.97		
17.75	82.25	607.3	62.66	37.34	36.39		
15.19	84.81	505.4	57.89	42.11	75.44		
0.0	100.0	408.6	0.0	100.0	56.37		B
2.78	97.22	387.5	0.0	100.0	56.08		
5.07	94.93	369.5	0.78	99.22	57.61		
6.71	93.29	356.5	0.67	99.33	57.01		
8.82	91.18	350.1	0.95	99.05	57.84		
9.18	90.82	341.1	0.0	100.0	55.58		
10.06	89.94	331.4	1.14	98.86	56.82		
10.61	89.39	327.8	45.94	54.06	28.29		
						Double salt + B Eutectic No.2.	

* Solid phase was too small for quantitative estimation

The experimental results can also be expressed according to Table II with the graphical representation of Jaenecke (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 81, 132) in Fig 2. The abscissa AB indicates the number of grams of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and copper sulphate in 100 g. of the dissolved anhydrous salts, and the ordinate shows the number of grams of water in which 100 g. of the mixture dissolved to give a saturated solution. The point A indicates 100 g. of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and 0 g. of copper sulphate, whereas the point B indicates *vice versa*.

FIG. 2

And any point on this line AB gives the composition of 100 g. of the mixture in the anhydrous state. It is evident from the diagram (Fig.2) that all the straight lines joining the points indicating the composition of the saturated solution and the corresponding separated solid phases pass through the point, which indicates the composition of the solid phase with which the various liquid phases are in equilibrium.

According to this method of representation, 63.60 g. of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate and 36.40 g. of CuSO_4 represent the molecular proportions. From

the diagram, it will be observed that a higher proportion of CuSO_4 is necessary for the stability of the double salt in solution at 30° .

From supersaturated solutions containing dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and copper sulphate, the following phases will crystallise out at 30° :

(i) Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, if copper sulphate does not exceed 41.44% in the solute.

(ii) The double salt, $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, if the amount of CuSO_4 lies between 41.44% and 89.39%.

(iii) Copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, if the amount of copper sulphate exceed 89.39% in the solute.

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA

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